

Uniqueness of a Meromorphic Functions Partially Shares a Small Functions with its Linear Difference Polynomial

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MSC 2010 Classification: Primary 30D35; Secondary 39A05, 39A10.

Keywords and phrases:

Partially shared values, linear difference polynomial, uniqueness, Meromorphic function, Nevanlinna theory.

Abstract:

Recently, some uniqueness theorems about a meromorphic function $f(z)$ with its shift as well as difference operators sharing three values CM have been obtained. In this paper, we have obtained the same conclusion as in the earlier results by considering weaker assumption on sharing and by considering the more general function than the shift operators. Furthermore as a particular cases of our results, we obtain various corollaries which greatly improve the earlier results due to Chen, Yi [4], Lü, Lü [18] L. Zhen [24] and Barki, Dyavanal, Bhoosnurmath [1] and others.

1. Introduction and the main results

By any meromorphic function f we always mean that it is defined on \mathbb{C} . We assume that the reader is familiar with the standard notations of Nevanlinna theory as given in [17, 21]. We recall that $T(r, f)$ denotes the Nevanlinna characteristic function of a non-constant meromorphic function f and $N\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) = N(r, a; f)$, $\left(\overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) = \overline{N}(r, a; f)\right)$ denotes the counting function (reduced counting function) of a -points of f . For $a = \infty$, we use $N(r, f) = N(r, \infty; f)$ denote counting function of poles of f . A function α is said to be a small function of meromorphic function f if it satisfies $T(r, \alpha) = o(T(r, f))$, where $r \rightarrow \infty$ outside of possible exceptional set of finite logarithmic measure.

The following definitions are used in the present paper.

Definition 1.1 [17] Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function in the finite complex plane \mathbb{C} . Here, the order $\rho(f)$ of $f(z)$ is defined by

$$\rho(f) = \overline{\lim}_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log T(r, f)}{\log r}$$

and the hyper-order $\rho_2(f)$ of $f(z)$ is defined by

$$\rho_2(f) = \overline{\lim}_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log \log T(r, f)}{\log r}.$$

Definition 1.2 [17] For a complex constant a , $\delta(a, f)$ is defined by

$$\delta(a, f) = 1 - \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N(r, a, f)}{T(r, f)},$$

Definition 1.3 [17] For a constant value a , we denote the set of all a -points(CM) of f by $E(a, f)$, and all distinct a -points(IM) of f by $\overline{E}(a, f)$. For two non-constant meromorphic functions f and g , we say f and g share the value a CM, if $E(a, f) = E(a, g)$. On the other hand, if $\overline{E}(a, f) = \overline{E}(a, g)$, we say f and g share the value a IM. Further we say that a meromorphic function f shares a partially CM with a meromorphic function g if $E(a, f) \subset E(a, g)$. Similarly meromorphic function f shares a partially IM with a meromorphic function g if $\overline{E}(a, f) \subset \overline{E}(a, g)$.

In this paper, we have used $L(z, f)$ is the linear shift polynomial of $f(z)$ as below

$$L(z, f) = b_n f(z + c_n) + \cdots + b_1 f(z + c_1) + b_0 f(z), \quad (1.1)$$

for a meromorphic function of order $\rho_2(f) < 1$ with $\sum_{i=0}^n b_i = b_0(z) + \cdots + b_n(z) \equiv 0$. In particular if we choose $\sum_{i=0}^n b_i = (-1)^i \binom{n}{i} (i = 0, \cdots, k)$, then it is easy to see that $L(z, f) = \Delta_c^n f(z)$.

The earlier result are as follows

In 2013, Chen, Yi [4] considered a meromorphic function which share three distinct values CM together with its first-order difference operator and obtained the following result.

Theorem A: [4] Let f be a transcendental meromorphic function such that its order of growth $\rho(f)$ is not an integer or infinite, and let $\eta \in \mathbb{C}$ be a constant, such that $f(z + \eta) \not\equiv f(z)$. If $\Delta f = f(z + \eta) - f(z)$ and $f(z)$ share the three distinct values a, b, ∞ CM, then $f(z + \eta) = 2f(z)$.

In 2017, Lü, Lü [18] proved that the above theorem A still holds for meromorphic functions of finite order. That is

Theorem B: [18] Let f be a transcendental meromorphic function of finite order, and let $\Delta f = f(z + c) - f(z) (\not\equiv 0)$, where $c \neq 0$ is a finite number. If Δf and f share three distinct values e_1, e_2, ∞ CM, then $\Delta f \equiv f$.

In 2019, L. Zhen [24] extended Theorem B by considering polynomials sharing instead of value sharing as below

Theorem C [24] Let f be a transcendental meromorphic function of finite order, and let $\Delta f = f(z+c) - f(z) (\neq 0)$, where $c \neq 0$ is a finite number. If Δf and f share three distinct polynomials P_1, P_2, ∞ CM, then $\Delta f \equiv f$.

In 2022, Barki, Dyavanal, Bhoosnurmamath [1] generalize Theorem C for higher order difference operator and proved the following theorem.

Theorem D [8] Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function of finite order such that $N(r, f) = S(r, f)$ and let $c \in \mathbb{C}$ be a constant such that $\Delta_c^n f(z) (\neq 0)$ and a, b be two non-zero distinct finite complex constants. If $\Delta_c^n f(z) = \sum_{r=0}^n (-1)^r \binom{n}{r} f(z + (n-r)c)$, where c is a non-zero complex number, $m \geq 1$ is a positive integer and $f(z)$ share a, b CM then $\Delta_c^n f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

By observing above theorems, the following questions are inevitable.

Question 1.1. Can sharing values CM in the theorem A-C be weakened to partially sharing values.

Question 1.2. Can sharing three constants be extended to sharing three small functions.

Question 1.3. Is it possible to extend the results of theorems A-D by considering more general linear polynomial in f than Δf and $\Delta^n f$.

Question 1.4. Can the condition on the order of a meromorphic function be weakened.

The main objective of the present paper is to give affirmative answer to all the above questions.

The first main theorem of this is as follows.

Theorem 1.1 Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and let $\alpha(z) \in \ker(L(z, f)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $L(z, f) (\neq 0)$ is of the form (1.1) and $E(0, f) \subset E(0, L(z, f))$, $E(\alpha(z), f) \subset E(\alpha(z), L(z, f))$, $E(\infty, L(z, f)) \subset E(\infty, f)$, then $L(z, f) \equiv f(z)$.

By considering the particular cases for $L(z, f)$, we have the following Corollaries.

If $L(z, f) = \Delta_c^n f(z)$ in Theorem 1.1, then theorem 1.1 reduces as the following Corollary.

Corollary 1.A Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$, and let $\alpha(z) \in \ker(\Delta_c^n f(z)) \cap S(r, f)$ such that $\Delta_c^n f(z) (\neq$

0) and $E(0, f) \subset E(0, \Delta_c^n f(z))$, $E(\alpha(z), f) \subset E(\alpha(z), \Delta_c^n f(z))$, $E(\infty, \Delta_c^n f(z)) \subset E(\infty, f)$ then $\Delta_c^n f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

If $n = 1$ in Corollary 1.A, then we have the following Corollary.

Corollary 1.B Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$, and let $\alpha(z) \in \ker(\Delta_c f(z)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $\Delta_c f(z) (\not\equiv 0)$ and $E(0, f) \subset E(0, \Delta_c f(z))$, $E(\alpha(z), f) \subset E(\alpha(z), \Delta_c f(z))$, $E(\infty, \Delta_c f(z)) \subset E(\infty, f)$ then $\Delta_c f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

Our next main theorem is as follows.

Theorem 1.2 Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $\alpha_1(z), \alpha_2(z) \in \ker(L(z, f)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $L(z, f) (\not\equiv 0)$ is of the form (1.1) and $E(\alpha_1, f) \subset E(\alpha_1, L(z, f))$, $E(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset E(\alpha_2(z), L(z, f))$, $E(\infty, L(z, f)) \subset E(\infty, f)$ and $\delta(0, f) > 0$, then $L(z, f) \equiv f(z)$.

As in the above if $L(z, f) = \Delta_c^n f(z)$ and $L(z, f) = \Delta_c f(z)$ we have the following Corollaries.

Corollary 1.C Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $\alpha_1(z), \alpha_2(z) \in \ker(\Delta_c^n f(z)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $\Delta_c^n f(z) (\not\equiv 0)$ and $E(\alpha_1, f) \subset E(\alpha_1, \Delta_c^n f(z))$, $E(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset E(\alpha_2(z), \Delta_c^n f(z))$, $E(\infty, \Delta_c^n f(z)) \subset E(\infty, f)$ and $\delta(0, f) > 0$, then $\Delta_c^n f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

Corollary 1.D Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $\alpha_1(z), \alpha_2(z) \in \ker(\Delta_c f(z)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $\Delta_c f(z) (\not\equiv 0)$ and $E(\alpha_1, f) \subset E(\alpha_1, \Delta_c f(z))$, $E(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset E(\alpha_2(z), \Delta_c f(z))$, $E(\infty, \Delta_c f(z)) \subset E(\infty, f)$ and $\delta(0, f) > 0$, then $\Delta_c f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

In the following theorem, we have considered three small functions that are shared by $f(z)$ and $L(z, f)$ for the case of an entire function.

Theorem 1.3 Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant entire function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $\alpha_1(z), \alpha_2(z), \alpha_3(z) \in \ker(L(z, f)) \cap S(r, f)$. $L(z, f) (\not\equiv 0)$ is of the form (1.1) and $\overline{E}(\alpha_1, f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_1, L(z, f))$, $\overline{E}(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_2(z), L(z, f))$, $\overline{E}(\alpha_3(z), f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_3(z), L(z, f))$ and $\delta(0, f) > 0$, then $L(z, f) \equiv f(z)$.

As above, we have the following Corollaries

Corollary 1.E Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant entire function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $\alpha_1(z), \alpha_2(z), \alpha_3(z) \in \ker(\Delta_c^n f(z)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $\Delta_c^n f(z) (\neq 0)$ and $\overline{E}(\alpha_1, f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_1, \Delta_c^n f(z))$, $\overline{E}(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_2(z), \Delta_c^n f(z))$, $\overline{E}(\alpha_3(z), f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_3(z), \Delta_c^n f(z))$ and $\delta(0, f) > 0$, then $\Delta_c^n f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

Corollary 1.F Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant entire function such that $\rho_2(f) < 1$ and $\alpha_1(z), \alpha_2(z), \alpha_3(z) \in \ker(\Delta_c f(z)) \cap S(r, f)$. If $\Delta_c f(z) (\neq 0)$ and $\overline{E}(\alpha_1, f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_1, \Delta_c f(z))$, $\overline{E}(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_2(z), \Delta_c f(z))$, $\overline{E}(\alpha_3(z), f) \subset \overline{E}(\alpha_3(z), \Delta_c f(z))$ and $\delta(0, f) > 0$, then $\Delta_c f(z) \equiv f(z)$.

2. Some preliminary results

To prove our theorems, we use the following known results

Lemma 2.1. [12,13] Let $f(z)$ be a meromorphic function with $\rho_2(f) < 1$, and let c be a non-zero complex number. Then

$$m\left(r, \frac{f(z+c)}{f(z)}\right) = S(r, f),$$

for all r outside of a set of finite logarithmic measure.

Lemma 2.2. [22] Let $f(z)$ be a non-constant meromorphic function on \mathbb{C} and let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_q be distinct meromorphic functions on \mathbb{C} . Assume that $a_i \in S(r, f)$ for all $(i = 1, 2, \dots, q)$. Then we have the second main theorem

$$(q-2)T(r, f) \leq \sum_{j=1}^q \overline{N}(r, a_j, f) + S(r, f),$$

for all r outside of a set of finite logarithmic measure.

The following lemma plays a vital role in proving our results.

Lemma 2.3. [14] Let M be a field containing all meromorphic function over \mathbb{C} and N be a subfield of M . Let $f \in N \setminus \ker(L)$, where $L : M \rightarrow M$ is a linear operator such that

$$m\left(r, \frac{L(f)}{f(z)}\right) = o(T(r, f)).$$

as $r \rightarrow \infty$ outside of an exceptional set $E \subset (0, \infty)$. If a_1, a_2, \dots, a_q are $q (\geq 1)$ different elements of $\ker(L) \cap S(r, f)$, then

$$(q-1)T(r, f) \leq N(r, f) + \sum_{j=1}^q \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a_j}\right) - N_{L(f)}(r, f) + S(r, f),$$

where $N_{L(f)}(r, f) = 2N(r, f) - N(r, L(f)) + N(r, \frac{1}{L(f)})$.

3. Proof of the main results

Proof of Theorem 1.1:

On the contrary, assume that $L(z, f) \not\equiv f(z)$. Since $L(z, f) \not\equiv 0$, consider

$$H(z) = \frac{L(z, f)}{f}.$$

As $E(0, f) \subset E(0, L(z, f))$ and $E(\infty, L(z, f)) \subset E(\infty, f)$, so it is clear that $H(z)$ is an entire function. Now using Lemma 2.1, we get

$$m(r, H(z)) = m(r, \frac{L(z, f)}{f}) = S(r, f).$$

This implies that

$$T(r, H(z)) = S(r, f). \quad (3.1)$$

Since $H(z) \not\equiv 1$, using (3.1) and the fact that $E(\alpha(z), f) \subset E(\alpha(z), L(z, f))$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha(z)}\right) &\leq N\left(r, \frac{f(z)}{L(z, f) - f(z)}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{H(z) - 1}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, H(z)) + S(r, f) \\ &= S(r, f). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

By the assumption, we have

$E(0, f) \subset E(0, L(z, f))$ and $E(\infty, L(z, f)) \subset E(\infty, f)$, it follows that

$$N\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) < N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(z, f)}\right) + S(r, f) \quad (3.3)$$

and

$$N(r, L(z, f)) < N(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.4)$$

Using (3.2)-(3.4) and Lemma 2.3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq N(r, f) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f - \alpha(z)}\right) \\ &\quad - 2N(r, f) + N(r, L(z, f)) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(z, f)}\right) + S(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq (N(r, L(z, f)) - N(r, f)) + \left(N(r, \frac{1}{f}) - N(r, \frac{1}{L(z, f)}) \right) + S(r, f) \\ &= S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Which is a contradiction. Hence $L(z, f) \equiv f(z)$.

Proof of Theorem 1.2:

$$\text{Let } H(z) = \frac{L(z, f)}{f}.$$

If $H(z) \equiv 1$, then we get $L(z, f) = f(z)$. So let us assume that $H(z) \not\equiv 1$. By Lemma 2.1 we have $m(r, H(z)) = S(r, f)$. As $E(\infty, L(z, f)) \subset E(\infty, f)$ so

$$T(r, H(z)) = N(r, H(z)) \leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + S(r, f). \quad (3.5)$$

Now, using $E(\alpha_1, f) \subset E(\alpha_2, L(z, f))$, $E(\alpha_2(z), f) \subset E(\alpha_2(z), L(z, f))$ yields

$$N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_1}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_2}\right) \leq N\left(r, \frac{f(z)}{L(z, f) - f(z)}\right) + S(r, f). \quad (3.6)$$

In view of (3.5), (3.6) and Lemma 2.3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq N(r, f) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_1(z)}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_2(z)}\right) \\ &\quad - 2N(r, f) + N(r, L(z, f)) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(z, f)}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq (N(r, L(z, f)) - N(r, f)) + N\left(r, \frac{f(z)}{L(z, f) - f(z)}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, H(z)) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

which yields that $\delta(0, f) = 0$, which is a contradiction to the hypothesis that $\delta(0, f) > 0$. Therefore $L(z, f) \equiv f(z)$.

Proof of Theorem 1.3:

Consider $H(z) = \frac{L(z, f)}{f}$.

If $H(z) \equiv 1$, then we get $L(z, f) = f(z)$. So let us assume that $H(z) \not\equiv 1$. As $f(z)$ is entire, $N(r, L(z, f)) \leq (n+1)N(r, f) + S(r, f) = S(r, f)$. This with Lemma 2.2, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_1}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_2}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f(z) - \alpha_2}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq N\left(r, \frac{f(z)}{L(z, f) - f(z)}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, H) + S(r, f) = N(r, H) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + N(r, L(z, f)) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

That is,

$$T(r, f) \leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + S(r, f). \quad (3.7)$$

The equation (3.8) implies $\delta(0, f) = 0$, which contradicts the given condition $\delta(0, f) > 0$. Hence $L(z, f) \equiv f(z)$.

4. Acknowledgment

The second author is supported by URS fellowship, Department of Mathematics, Karnatak University, Dharwad, Ref. No. KU/Sch/URS/2019-2020/616.

References

- [1] M. Barki, R. S. Dyavanal, and S. S. Bhoosnurmath, Uniqueness of a meromorphic function sharing two values CM with its difference operator, Indian J. pure. Appl math. (2022), <http://doi.org/10.1007/s13226-021-00196-4>
- [2] S. S. Bhoosnurmath and R. S. Dyavanal, Uniqueness of meromorphic functions sharing sets, Bull. Math. Anal. Appl., 3(2011), No. 3, 200-208.
- [3] Y. M. Chiang and S. J. Feng, On the Nevanlinna characteristic of $f(z+c)$ and difference equations in the complex plane. Ramanujan J., 16(2008), 105-129.
- [4] Z. X. Chen and H. X. Yi, On sharing values of meromorphic functions and their differences, Results Math., 63(2013), 557-565.
- [5] S. Chen, On uniqueness of meromorphic functions and their difference operators with partially shared values, Comput. Meth. Funct. Th., (2018).
- [6] R. S. Dyavanal and A. M. Hattikal, Unicity theorems on difference polynomials of meromorphic functions sharing one value, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematical Sciences, 9(2016), No. 2, 89-98.
- [7] R. S. Dyavanal and A. M. Hattikal, Weighted sharing of uniqueness of difference polynomials of meromorphic functions, Far East journal of Mathematical Sciences, 98(2015), No. 3, 293-313.

- [8] R. S. Dyavanal and A. M. Hattikal, Uniqueness of difference-differential polynomials of entire functions sharing one value, *Tamkang J. Math.*, 47(2016), No. 2, 193-206.
- [9] R. S. Dyavanal, A. M. Hattikal and M. M. Mathai, Uniqueness of meromorphic functions sharing a set in annuli, *Cubo.*, 18(2016), No. 1, 1-14.
- [10] R. S. Dyavanal and R. V. Desai, Uniqueness of difference polynomials of meromorphic functions with weighted sharing, *Indian J. Math.*, 60(2018), No. 3, 439-456.
- [11] R. S. Dyavanal, M. M. Mathai and A. M. Hattikal, Unicity theorems of a linear difference polynomial of entire and meromorphic functions, *Indian J. Math.*, 61(2019), No. 1, 141-152.
- [12] R. G. Halburd and R. Korhonen, Nevanlinna theory for the difference operator, *Ann. Acad. Sci. Fenn. Math.*, 94(2006), 463-478.
- [13] R. G. Halburd and R. Korhonen, Difference analogue of the lemma on logarithmic derivative with applications to difference equations, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, 314(2006), 477-487.
- [14] R. G. Halburd and R. Korhonen, Value distribution and linear operators, *Proceedings of the Edinburgh Mathematical Society*(2014)57, 493-504
- [15] J. Heittokangas, R. Korhonen, I. Laine and J. Rieppo, Uniqueness of meromorphic functions sharing values with their shifts, *Complex Var. Elliptic.*, 56(2011), 81-92.
- [16] J. Heittokangas, R. Korhonen, I. Laine, J. Rieppo and J. Zhang, Value sharing results for shifts of meromorphic function and sufficient conditions for periodicity, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 355(2009), 352-363.
- [17] W. K. Hayman, *Meromorphic functions*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1964.
- [18] F. Lü and W. R. Lü, Meromorphic functions sharing three values with their difference operators, *Comput. Meth. Funct. Th.*, 17(2017), No. 3, 395-403.
- [19] S. Li and B. Q. Chen, Unicity of meromorphic functions sharing sets with their linear difference polynomials, *Abstr. Appl. Anal.*, (2014), ID:894968 7 pages.
- [20] V. Noulorvang and D. T. Pham, On partial value sharing results of meromorphic functions with their shifts and its applications, *Bull. Korean Math. Soc.* 57(2020), no. 5, 1083-1094.
- [21] C. C. Yang and H. X. Yi, *Uniqueness Theory of Meromorphic Functions*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht 2003, Chinese Original Science Press, Beijing, 1995.
- [22] K. Yamanoi, The second main theorem for small functions and related problems, *Acta Math.* 192(2004), no. 2, 225-294.
- [23] J. Zhang and L. W. Liao, Entire functions sharing some values with their difference operators, *Sci. China Ser. A.*, 57(2014), No. 10, 2143-2152.
- [24] L. Zhen, Meromorphic functions sharing three polynomials with their difference operators, *J. Contemp. math. Anal.* 54(2019), no. 5, 296-301; translated from *Izv. Nats. Akad. Nauk Armenii Mat.* 54(2019), no. 5, 44-52.